

Revealing the impact of CZTSe/CdS interface fluctuations on PV device performance through big data analysis assisted by machine learning methods

Jon Garí-Galíndez,^{1,2} Fabien Atlan,¹ Jacob Andrade-Arvizu,¹ Robert Fonoll-Rubio,¹ David Payno,¹ Enric Grau-Luque,¹ Alejandro Pérez-Rodríguez,^{1,3} Ignacio Becerril-Romero,^{1} Maxim Guc,¹ Victor Izquierdo-Roca,¹ Pedro Vidal-Fuentes^{1*}*

¹Catalonia Institute for Energy Research – IREC, 08930 Sant Adrià de Besòs, Barcelona, Spain

²Departament de Física, Campus Nord B4-B5, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, E-08034 Barcelona, Spain

³Departament d'Enginyeria Electrònica i Biomèdica, IN²UB, Universitat de Barcelona, 08028 Barcelona, Spain

*E-mail: Ignacio Becerril-Romero (ibecerril@irec.cat) and Pedro Vidal-Fuentes (pvidal@irec.cat)

Keywords: Machine learning, accelerated research, interfaces, thin film photovoltaics, kesterites, fluctuations

This work showcases the importance of development suitable inspection and analysis methodologies with high statistical relevance data coupled with machine learning algorithms, for the detection, control and understanding of small fluctuations in the scale up of thin film photovoltaics to industrial sizes. To exhibit this methodology, this work investigates the effect of subtle inhomogeneities on the efficiency of thin film solar cells based on the $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4/\text{CdS}$ interface using two large area samples subdivided in ~400 individual solar cells. A large dataset obtained from Raman and photoluminescence spectroscopic techniques together with J-V optoelectronic data is generated to elucidate the impact of these inhomogeneities on the efficiency of the devices. Using a combination of statistical (spectral difference) and over 440000 multivariate polynomial regressions through machine learning algorithms, it is revealed how the main limiting factor for device performance are subtle fluctuations in the nanostructure and surface defects of the CdS layer, rather than compositional fluctuations or defects in the kesterite absorber. It is estimated that their avoidance could account for a 2% (absolute) increase in device efficiency, opening a possible way for the kesterite community towards the improvement of the technology.

1 Introduction

The scale-up and industrialization of emerging thin film solar cell technologies based on sustainable materials is regarded as the most promising roadmap towards increasing the penetration and adoption of solar energy as a real alternative to traditional non-

renewable energy sources. This transition from laboratory-scale small cells to more wide formats is essential and it paves the way towards diverse applications, not just extensive solar farms, but also for distributed implementations like IoT, indoor PV, and various emerging paradigms.^[1-3] Materials from the $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$ (CZTSSe) family, also known as kesterites, have surfaced as a promising contender in this regard, owing to their stability, affordability, adaptability to flexible substrates, tunable bandgap and their Earth-abundant elemental composition.^[4-13] Laboratory efficiencies exceeding 15% have been reported demonstrating the real potential of the technology.^[14-16]

Thin film solar cells, as those based on kesterites, are highly complex systems made of heterogeneous multilayer stacks, typically comprised by 6 or more different nano- and micro-layers. The properties of these layers control the final performance of the resulting solar cell device in such a way that small variations in any of them can have a significant or even critical effect in the final optoelectronic parameters. For CZTSSe-based solar cells even subtle compositional, morphological or structural deviations and the recombination mechanisms associated with those can detrimentally influence device efficiency and place a limit to the V_{oc} .^[17-20] More specifically, the interactions between the commonly used CdS electron transport layer (ETL) and the CZTSSe layer are crucial and responsible for most of the limiting factors of the devices, reflected, for example in non-optimal band alignment, fermi level pinning, interface defects and formation of secondary phases.^[21-22]

These effects are even more pronounced when trying to scale up the technology which uncovers challenges that warrant attention. In fact, in mature thin film technologies such as chalcopyrite-based, the typically encountered cell-to-module efficiency gap ($\Delta PCE_{cell-module}$) is around 5% (absolute) which underscores the importance of addressing these limitations upfront.^[23] One of the most relevant factors for commercialization contributing to the $\Delta PCE_{cell-module}$ is homogeneity, as the defects and deviations described above are more likely to appear in larger areas leading to an overall decreased efficiency. These issues need to be comprehended and minimized for technology industrialization.^[24]

Controlling the homogeneity entails dual aspects: comprehending the underlying physical or chemical mechanisms that lead to the appearance of the unwanted defects and the quantification of their implications on final device performance.^[25] These, which might be subtle micro/nano-scale variations, are difficult to observe at small laboratory scales. As such, their study requires, on the one hand, large and more comprehensive datasets of actual physical and chemical properties of the materials in finished operating devices to create a complete model of the system and, on the other hand, the application of novel advanced data analysis techniques to deal with such amounts of data.

In this regard, recent advancements in machine learning have significantly improved material discovery,^[26] analysis and optimization of thin film solar cells. Various algorithms have been employed in the field of photovoltaics to find the underlying answer of various problems. Supervised learning techniques, such as decision trees, random forest (RF), and Support Vector Machines (SVM), have been widely used for classification and regression tasks, enabling accurate predictions of solar cell performance based mostly on fabrication parameters.^[27-29] Additionally, unsupervised learning methods, like CART, clustering algorithms like XGboost, dimension reduction algorithms like principal component analysis (PCA) and linear discriminant analysis (LDA) have been effective in identifying patterns and reducing dimensionality in large datasets, generating useful

classifications and facilitating better understanding of the limiting factors.^[30-32] These diverse machine learning approaches collectively contribute to the advancement of thin-film solar cell technology by providing robust analytical tools.

While the applications of these tools are essential and will be ubiquitous in the near future, the current bottleneck lies on the difficulty to obtain big data from characterization techniques. Since classical analysis approaches were focused on slow and precise measurements of material properties, much of the research is prone to rely on (i) simulated data, (ii) literature data collection, (iii) synthesis parameters or (iv) focus on material discovery.^[26-28, 30, 33-35] Regarding (i) and (iv) the primary concern is that simulations often rely on idealized models and assumptions that may not capture the full extent of material defects, impurities, and most importantly overlook complex interactions between different layers and components of thin-film PV cells that occur during the fabrication process.^[36] On the other hand, (ii) and (iii), present some problems on material sciences as there is no standardization of the synthesis or characterization equipment (with some exceptions such as certifications from external sources). This means that, for example, parameters like temperature, thickness, pressure... are not straightforward transferrable from one set-up to another, or even in between experimental runs in the same equipment (degradation, external factors, damage, spatial/temporal inhomogeneities, etc...). Our study differs from all the mentioned approaches by relying on consistent synthesis conditions and the analysis of material properties using real physicochemical data acquired by non-destructive spectroscopic techniques in finished operational solar cells. This approach allows capturing the intrinsic variability and complexity associated with actual device performance, providing more reliable and relevant insights for optimizing material properties and manufacturing processes.

In this context, this research investigates two large area $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$ $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ (CZTSe) samples synthesized with the same conditions (same input process parameters) and discretized in $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ devices (~400 solar cells). These two samples make possible to test fluctuations at two levels, inside the same experimental run (in-sample variation) and between runs (sample-to-sample variation). As such, instead of employing data from the synthesis conditions (process parameters), this work is based on the direct use of data from the physicochemical properties of the materials in finalized working devices. The data used for the analysis was extracted from the characterization of each individual discretized device by spectroscopic techniques (multiwavelength Raman and photoluminescence spectroscopies), which were combined with the optoelectronic parameters extracted from J-V curves of each device. The data obtained was filtered by the statistical analysis and fitting of the acquired spectra, generating a dataset of more than 40 predictors with the optoelectronic parameters (J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF , PCE) as target values. This dataset was analyzed by simple Machine Learning methods based on multivariate polynomial regressions (all the possibilities, in the order of 440000) to find the most representative combination of predictors that can best explain the observed optoelectronics without losing any physical meaning in the process. Following this approach, we are able to identify that one specific defect of the CdS layer, rather than variations in the CZTSe absorber layer, has the most representative correlation with the V_{oc} of the individual discretized solar cell devices explaining. The correlation found explain the 80 mV voltage loss observed between the analyzed devices, and, thus, allows concluding that the defect in the CdS layer is the main limiting factor for the scale-up of the CZTSe/CdS solar cell technology analyzed in this work. Since the latest record

kesterite devices are based on the CZTSe/CdS interface,^[14-16] the results presented here are very relevant for the whole kesterite community in the quest towards the industrialization of this promising PV technology. Furthermore, this work serves as an example of the potential of the employed methodology, which may be applied to the study of other complex systems either inside or outside the thin film PV research field, highlighting the necessity of transitioning towards large datasets and advanced statistical and machine learning methods based in experimental data to accelerate research and to define the main technology limitations.

2 Results and discussions

2.1 Methodology workflow

The workflow proposed in this study is based on five sequential steps (Figure 1):

- 1) Acquisition of experimental data of the discretized cells through spectroscopic and optoelectronic techniques (Figure 2).
- 2) Statistical analysis of the acquired spectra and selection of predictors (Section 2.2).
- 3) Creation of a coherent database by merging the predictors with the acquired optoelectronic data (labeling) (Section 2.3).
- 4) Numerical model creation assisted by machine learning based on multivariate polynomial regression approach (Section 2.3).
- 5) Validation of the model and in-depth physico-chemical analysis to obtain fundamental information of the system (Section 2.4).

Figure 1. Diagram of the workflow followed on this study. Dashed boxes indicates the sections of the manuscript where the different steps are discussed. Solid color boxes show the actions performed.

Figure 2: a) Schematic representation of the devices inside the sample b) Sample description with a device identified and measuring spots. c) IREC's proprietary Raman and PL probe (the laser source and the spectrometer are connected to the probe by optical fibers) attached to a micrometric precision X-Y stage programmable to move from cell to cell, for the automation of the acquisition of the spectroscopic data. d) Solar simulator stage, in which the optoelectronic measurements of the ~200 cells are done by contacting each cell with a tip on the front contact while maintaining the back contact fixed to all cells.

2.2 Sample description and characterization

The results of the present study were achieved using two 5x5 cm² CZTSe-based samples fabricated during the development of IREC's kesterite thin film PV baseline process. The details of the manufacturing process can be found in the Methodology section. To probe and map the in-sample homogeneity of all the samples produced within the baseline process, these are mechanically scribed into 3x3 mm² individual solar cells and the optoelectronic properties of each "pixel" discretized device are measured. In this way more than 40 samples with 196 solar cell each have already been produced and the dispersion of the efficiency in each sample can be seen in the form of boxplots in Figure 3a . Following the progress of the development of the baseline kesterite PV devices presented in the figure, it can be observed that there is some uncontrollable part of the production process that results in an in-sample inhomogeneity of the optoelectronic properties at the 5x5 cm² scale. To shed light on the main factors behind this large-scale efficiency inhomogeneities, this work focuses on analyzing the CZTSe/CdS interface of two selected samples using a combination of optoelectronic and spectroscopic techniques.

The optoelectronic characteristics of the samples employed for this study (sample A and sample B) are presented in Figure 3b. These samples were synthesized with 2-months difference and present spatial variations in their composing layers (all the synthesis processes are independent for each sample). This permits to construct a library of the fluctuations that emerge when scaling-up the technology to 5x5 cm². In particular, this library of fluctuations is created as a result of the mechanical scribing performed in the samples explained above that results in a total of 392 individual solar cells with slightly different characteristics (Surface mappings of the optoelectronic characteristics can be found on Figure S1). This approach allows for statistical analyses that are typically unattainable in smaller-scale samples.^[37]

The optoelectronic parameters of the 392 individual devices in the selected samples shown in Figure 3b were obtained from the illuminated J-V measurements acquired by contacting the top TCO layer of each cell and the common molybdenum back contact layer. There are some clear dissimilarities between both samples, being the most

prominent one in the V_{oc} of both samples with sample B presenting overall higher values. There are also differences in the fill factor (FF) which can be attributed to differences in the series and shunt resistance (see Figure S2 in the Supporting Information). These can be ascribed to the lower adherence of the CZTSe absorber layer to the Mo back contact in sample A that can be seen in the cross-section SEM images in Figure S3. On the other hand, the short circuit current (J_{sc}) does not show any prominent difference between the samples. All these variations result in a different average power conversion efficiency (PCE): $6.3 \pm 0.6 \%$ for sample A, and $7.5 \pm 0.5 \%$ for sample B. Since this work focuses on researching the main limiting factors of the scaled-up kesterite technology in general and not from specific samples, it should be noted that, from now on, the solar cells of the two samples will be mainly considered as a single library of data.

Figure 3. a) – Historical evolution and statistical (box plot) distribution of the efficiency of all the $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$ samples fabricated within IREC’s kesterite thin film PV baseline process. The samples circled with a dashed line are those employed for the present study. b) – Box plot and statistical distribution of the main optoelectronic parameters of the two $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$ samples selected for the present study. (IQR: interquartile range)

To study the physicochemical mechanisms behind the distributions in the optoelectronic parameters, the front CdS/CZTSe interface of the full devices were characterized by multi-wavelength Raman spectroscopy (RS) and photoluminescence spectroscopy (PL) under 442 nm (to probe the CdS layer) and 532 nm (to probe the surface of the CZTSe layer) excitation wavelengths. Both techniques are compatible with the mapping of large areas (with an adequate setup) and have already demonstrated a high potential for the fundamental study of thin film materials and devices and to detect subtle, but still relevant, changes in the physicochemical properties that correlate with the final performance of thin film solar cells. Moreover, the combination of RS and PL spectroscopies with optoelectronic analyses has already proven to be a powerful approach to provide direct insights about the main limitations of the thin film technologies both in lab and at larger production scales.^[25,38,39]

The spectra resulting from the characterization of the samples through RS and PL are shown in Figure 4, together with the average spectrum of the whole set of spectra (black solid lines) and spectral difference (bottom insets) of each sample. Focusing first on the absorber layer, the results from RS measured under 532 nm show mainly the characteristic spectrum of a CZTSe kesterite type compound with the main bands at 170 cm^{-1} , 194 cm^{-1} and 215 – 260 cm^{-1} comprised by the A^2+E/B , A^1 and E/B symmetry peaks, respectively (Figure 4a). No indication of secondary phases can be seen in any of the spectra.^[18,40,41] Additionally, at 303 cm^{-1} , the LO peak (LO components of A_1 and E_1 symmetry modes) of the CdS is also detectable.^[42,43] The spectral difference (which points out the regions where there is spectral variation among the spectra) in this case allows detecting some slight changes in the main Raman band at 194 cm^{-1} , mainly related to peak position and slight variation of its full width at half maximum (FWHM). According to previous findings, these changes can be related with the variation of the Cu/Zn disorder in the crystalline lattice of the kesterite compound.^[44] Additionally, clearer variations of the intensity of the band at 170 cm^{-1} can also be observed and can be explained by both by changes in Cu/Zn disorder and in the concentration of $[\text{Zn}_{\text{Cu}}+\text{V}_{\text{Cu}}]$ cluster defects. Following the methodology proposed in Ref. [44], it can be concluded that changes in the cluster defect concentration prevail over the change in the Cu/Zn disorder. Finally, changes in the intensity of the CdS peak at 303 cm^{-1} are also detected. These are explored in detail below in the analysis of the Raman spectra measured under 442 nm.

Figure 4: RS and PL spectra measured under 442 and 532 nm. The average spectrum is displayed as a solid line (black in case of RS and colored in case of PL) and the spectral differences (calculated in the spectra normalized to the maximum intensity) are shown at the bottom of each graph.

Continuing with the analysis of the CZTSe absorber layer, deeper insights about its optoelectronic characteristics are obtained through the PL spectra measured under 532 nm (Figure 4b). The main emission band with its maximum located around 1 eV can be associated to the CZTSe phase, as well as a low energy contribution at around 0.9 eV. The nature of the observed bands was thoroughly discussed in previous works and can be found elsewhere.^[45-47] The spectral difference reveals minor differences within and between both samples. On the one hand, a 0.03 eV shift of the PL band maximum between both samples can be observed and could be explained by the differences in the composition of the absorber layer (see Table 1) as discussed in Ref. [45]. Concerning intra-sample spectral variations, the main differences are found in band intensity with no significant variations in band position or shape. These variations complement the Raman

spectroscopy measurements of the CZTSe absorber layer, showing just subtle in-sample variations of its physicochemical properties. Moreover, while the data shown do not allow to quantify the absolute photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY), the high stability of the system employed for acquiring the data allows directly associating the observed changes in the PL band intensity exclusively with changes in the PLQY.

Moving to the analysis on the CdS layer, Figure 4c shows the RS spectra obtained under 442 nm. The spectra reveal mainly peaks linked to the CdS phase: the main one around $\sim 300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ associated to the LO mode, and another at $\sim 600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ associated with the overtone of the first LO mode, referred to as 2LO peak.^[42,43] The appearance of this overtone is attributed to the fact that the measurements were made close to resonance conditions (i.e. when the excitation wavelength is close to the fundamental optical transition of the material).^[48-50] The spectral difference shows in-sample fluctuations in the absolute intensity of the recorded spectra, which are closely related to changes in the thickness of the CdS layer.^[51] This is supported by the clear presence of the main Raman peak of the CZTSe absorber in all the spectra, which indicates that the integration volume of the RS surpasses the layer thickness (50 – 100 nm) and, in these conditions, changes in absolute intensity are directly connected to the measured volume (i.e. thickness) of the layer. Previous works show that this thickness variation is a result of the deposition process and was shown to be close linked to device performance.^[52] While subtle, there are further variations in the spectra besides layer thickness. The most notable differences can be observed in the profile of the CdS peak, where the LO mode displays slight variations in the FWHM as symmetric shifts on both sides of the central wavenumber ($\sim 300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The shoulders of the CdS-LO at ~ 271 and 344 cm^{-1} (named in Figure 4c as Def1 and Def2, respectively), often associated with a CdS-TO mode ($\sim 240 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), present an intriguing puzzle involving possible contributions from surface optical phonons (SOP), hexagonal and cubic CdS structures or a combination of them.^[53-55] This complexity and inhomogeneity of the buffer layer is further evidenced in the FE-SEM top view images (Figure S4), which reveal two distinct types of morphology: agglomerated CdS particles resulting from the large-scale inhomogeneous chemical bath deposition (CBD) process,^[56] and uniform coverage constituted by apparent CdS platelets. These platelets, expected to exhibit strong confinement effects in one dimension, strengthen the hypothesis of assigning the band at $\sim 271 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to SOP. This is further supported by the changes in intensity of the 2LO mode.

The observations made above about the characteristics of the CdS layer are further confirmed by the analysis of the PL spectra measured under 442 nm excitation shown in Figure 4d. Considering the high interaction of the excitation wavelength employed with the CdS layer (close to resonant conditions), the observed PL bands can be directly ascribed with the optical transitions inside the layer. The band at higher energy (2.44 – 2.53 eV) is the band-to-band transition, showcasing subtle inter- and intra-sample variations. The more interesting variations appear in the low energy broad band around 1.8 eV, which is attributed to deep trap states arising from surface-localized defects in accordance to previous studies.^[57-60] This interpretation also aligns with the platelet-like morphology of the CdS layer seen in Figure S4. Throughout the manuscript, this band will be referred to as the "defect" band.

2.3 Relevant spectral predictors and multivariate polynomial regressions

The results presented in the previous section show the complex although subtle nature of the structural and chemical variations in the CZTSe and CdS layers. These variations can be extracted from the spectral differences presented in the bottom insets of Figure 4. However, even when the spectral difference allows defining small spectral variation ranges, identifying which of the spectral parameters (i.e. peak position, FWHM or intensity) are the most relevant is not straightforward, very time consuming and prone to confirmation bias. Moreover, a significant change in one of the parameters may hinder more subtle (but still relevant) changes in others. As result, the sole use of the spectral difference statistical approach limits possible relevant information that can be extracted from the data and the definition of the spectral parameters that describe the full system. To elucidate which parameter shows the highest impact on device performance, several spectral predictors (parameters) were extracted through the fitting of the spectra for each characterization technique and wavelength employed. The fitting performed is a combination of Lorentzian and Gaussian curves as previously described in other works.^[61-64] An example of each of the fitting functions employed is presented in Figure 5. From each peak in the spectra its position, FWHM and intensity are extracted as spectral predictors. Then a data matrix is composed with all these parameters and correlated with the optoelectronic parameters of each device. In this way, a data library matrix consisting in 44 predictors for each of the 392 individual solar cell was generated (dataset). A nomenclature <Parameter/Technique/Peak number> for easily identifying the predictors was created and is schematically represented in Figure 6. This nomenclature will be used throughout the text.

To analyze the collected data a model based on multivariate polynomial regressions is used as a pointer to the predictor (or combination of predictors) that affect the most the optoelectronic parameters of the ~400 solar cells. These regressions considered all the possible combinations of up to 5 predictors as input variables in polynomial equations with degree ranging from 1 to 3, with the V_{oc} , J_{sc} , FF and PCE as targets (Eq. (1)). To perform these multivariate polynomial regressions and find the models, ML algorithms were employed using the *PolynomialFeatures* and *LinearRegression* functions of the *Scikit-learn* library in Python.^[65] The result is a total of around 440000 combinations for each optoelectronic parameter, which are ordered by their R^2 values.

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_1^2 + \beta_4 X_2^2 + \beta_5 X_1 X_2 + \dots + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1) y is the target optoelectronic parameter, X_x stands for the predictors and β_x are the weight coefficients. For instance, for FF as the target parameter, X_1 may correspond to <Max-Height/PL-532nm/Peak1> (intensity of the PL band 1 measured under 532 nm), X_2 may correspond to <FWHM/RS-532nm/Peak2> (FWHM of the second Raman peak measured under 532 nm), and if the weight coefficients for both predictors are comparable, they have comparable influence on the FF .

Figure 5: Examples of the fitting functions (green line) by individual peaks (orange line) of the spectra employed for: a) RS-532nm, b) PL-532nm, d) RS-442nm and d) PL-442nm.

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the nomenclature employed for identifying the predictors.

To compare the resulting models (descriptive equations) from the multivariate polynomial regressions and determine the optimal one, cross-validation (CV) tests were performed for calculating both the mean squared error (MSE) and the R^2 score of the data for each model. The CV results of all the regressions made for each optoelectronic parameter are shown in Figure 7. The results show that the best R^2 score, reaching a value of 0.75, are obtained for the V_{oc} , which means that this is the parameter for which the predictors calculated have the highest influence and can better model it. This is followed by the PCE and FF for which the R^2 scores of the best models are above 0.5. Finally, for J_{sc} , the R^2 of the best model is under 0.4. In contrast to the case of the V_{oc} , this means that there does not exist a polynomial model based on the selected predictors that can explain the behavior of the J_{sc} correctly, which will be discussed further in the text. This could be likely improved by including the analysis of other layers to increase the number of predictors for example by using additional excitation wavelengths.

Figure 7: R^2 values obtained from the CV tests of all the polynomial regressions as a function of the polynomial degree and number of predictors involved for each optoelectronic parameter. The different colors correspond to the different degrees of the polynomial equations used.

Another conclusion that can be obtained from Figure 7 is that the second-degree polynomials reach the best R^2 results for all the optoelectronic parameters, which discards the need of using of any third-degree relationships. On the other hand, and as expected, the performance of the models improves with the higher number of predictors employed in the regression. However, for the sake of simplicity and to ensure a good physical meaning, it seems logical to favor good performance models with the lowest minimum number of the involved predictors. The best models of the polynomial regression for each optoelectronic parameter based on their MSE and R^2 score are

presented in Table S1 in the Supporting Information. There, it can be observed that certain predictors appear recurrently, like <Max-Height/PL-442nm/Peak1> or <Max-Height/RS-442nm/Peak2>. In all the cases, there are several models with different number of parameters but with similarly high R^2 scores and, thus, with a similar performance, which reinforces the criterion of seeking the model with more simplicity and physical meaning.

Focusing on the V_{oc} , Table S1 shows that the best model (R^2 score of 0.743) is obtained with a second-degree polynomial with 5 predictors. From the predictors involved in the model, four are related to the CdS layer (<Max-Height/RS-442nm/Peak2>, <Center-Max/RS-442nm/Peak3>, <Center-Max/RS-442nm/Peak7> and <Max-Height/RS-532nm/Peak6>) and only one (<Center-Max/RS-532nm/Peak2>) is related to the CZTSe absorber layer. A more general look at all the good performance ($R^2 > 0.5$) models generated for the V_{oc} , mainly predictors related to the CdS layer appear, while predictors related to the CZTSe layers are less relevant. As explained above, following the criterion of simplicity to ensure the physical meaning of the model, a model with a second-degree polynomial, with three predictors (all related to the CdS layer), and with an R^2 score of 0.718 is selected as the optimum one instead of the more complex model with 5 predictors and higher R^2 score of 0.743 described above. Its descriptive equation is displayed below (Eq. (2)) together with the calculated values of the weight parameters:

$$V_{oc} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_1^2 + \beta_5 X_2^2 + \beta_6 X_3^2 + \beta_7 X_1 X_2 + \beta_8 X_1 X_3 + \beta_9 X_2 X_3 \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$X_1 = \text{<Max-Height/RS-442nm/Peak2>}$$

$$X_2 = \text{<Center-Max/RS-442nm/Peak3>}$$

$$X_3 = \text{<Max-Height/RS-532nm/Peak6>}$$

$$\beta_0 = -(8.0408508 \pm 0.0000008) \times 10^6; \beta_1 = -(5.78 \pm 0.06) \times 10^2; \beta_2 = (5.3464 \pm 0.0003) \times 10^4; \beta_3 = (3.609 \pm 0.060) \times 10^3; \beta_4 = (2.72 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-3}; \beta_5 = (1.92 \pm 0.02) \times 10^0; \beta_6 = -(3.74 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-2}; \beta_7 = -(8.887 \pm 0.001) \times 10^1; \beta_8 = -(1.20 \pm 0.02) \times 10^1; \beta_9 = -(1.21 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-1}.$$

In these cases, the 0.02 difference in the R^2 of the optimal and the best performing model can be considered negligible if taking into account the higher simplicity and, furthermore, regarding the fact that most of the weight coefficients of the second-degree terms of the equation (β_4 , β_5 , β_6 and β_9) are close to zero or significantly smaller than the others further simplifying the model. In this model, all the predictors represent exclusively variations in the CdS layer. Namely, the changes in the intensity of peak 2 and position of peak 3 of the Raman spectra measured under 442 nm excitation are assigned to variations in the defects of the CdS layer, or to the inhomogeneously distributed agglomerated particles, while the changes in the intensity of the peak 6 from the Raman spectra measured under 532 nm can be assigned to changes in the thickness of the CdS layer. The mappings of the 3 predictors and the prediction of the model can be found in the supporting information (Figure S5).

To deepen into the performance of the selected model, the real V_{oc} was compared with the values predicted by the model. In this case, CV was performed by dividing the 392 individual solar cells in five equal groups. The validation was made using 4 groups for training the model (i.e. calculate the weight coefficients), and the fifth group for validation

(i.e. for V_{oc} prediction). The result is shown in Figure 8 and allow concluding that the model can predict the V_{oc} properly and that the slope is near to one, indicating that the predicted values are close to the real ones. An exemption is found for the CV Test 2 dataset that presents worse results, which is due to relatively small size of the full data set (Figure S6). Overall, this validation test suggests that the predictive power of the model created for the V_{oc} is around 0.7, which is also close to the R^2 value of the model. An increase of the size of the dataset would probably improve the predictive power of the model.

Figure 8: Parity plot of the model result comparing the predictions of the model and the real measured V_{oc} including test and train datasets. Dots represent the V_{oc} values for each solar cell, lines represent a linear fit of the dots, and dispersion is shown as pale colored areas around the lines.

As mentioned above, in the case of the J_{sc} it was not possible to define a combination of predictors that generate a model with acceptable R^2 scores. This might be related to the smallest relative variation of this optoelectronic parameter across the whole dataset compared to the others (e.g., the standard deviation of the J_{sc} is 3.8 % and for V_{oc} is 5.0 %), and with a normal distribution. The extension of the analysis to other layers of the devices (e.g., HTL MoSe₂ layer on the back, or i-ZnO layer on the front) to increase the number of available predictors may result in the generation of model with better R^2 for the J_{sc} . In the case of the FF , the models with the highest R^2 include not only predictors directly related to the CdS variations but also predictors related to the CZTSe layer (e.g., <Center-Max/PL-532nm/Peak1> or <Max-Height/RS-532nm/Peak2>). These predictors are mainly related to variations in point defects, like the $[Zn_{Cu}+V_{Cu}]$ cluster defect, or to other variations in the electronic structure of the absorber layer. However, the R^2 values for the FF , are still relatively low (0.480), which suggests that, similarly to the case of J_{sc} , other predictors from other layers should be considered to get a more holistic picture of the relevant changes in the solar cells that influence this optoelectronic parameter. Finally, the PCE value, being a combination of the other three optoelectronic parameters described above, exhibits R^2 scores between the ones obtained for the V_{oc} , J_{sc} and FF , as expected, and a combination of predictors related to both to the CdS and CZTSe

layers. In this case, even though it is possible to find a meaningful combination of predictors with relatively high R^2 value (close to 0.6), the lack of information from the other layers of the devices still limits the possibility of building a more complete model for explaining the behavior of the PCE. A general view on the relevant predictors for each optoelectronic parameter presented in Table S1 allows concluding that only some of the 44 predictors defined have a real influence on the optoelectronic parameters of the kesterite PV devices, while most of present no relevance. In this regard, we consider the results as a success due to the use of real physicochemical parameters of the materials composing the solar cells, fabricated with the same synthesis conditions and arriving at prediction powers of up to 0.75 for the V_{oc} . In comparison with most of the literature which is based on prediction upon modification of synthesis parameters (strong variations, with impressive results),^[26, 30] our approach is key to demonstrate the feasibility of production control in industrial environments where the reproducibility of an established process is paramount to ensure high quality production. From our point of view, ML learning algorithms based on synthesis conditions in combination with ML methodologies applied to the analysis of in-situ physicochemical properties is key to enable closed cycle in-line process monitoring in industrial environments and true automated/accelerated research.

2.4 Main limiting factors of device performance

From the results presented above, it is clear that there is a surprising lack of correlation between the V_{oc} and the predictors associated to the CZTSe absorber layer. These include parameters influenced by $[Zn_{Cu}+V_{Cu}]$ defect clusters, as indicated by the relative integrated intensity of Raman band at 170 cm^{-1} and the asymmetry of the main CZTSe peak (see Figure 4). In contrast, the V_{oc} value of the kesterite solar cells appears to be predominantly controlled by the characteristic defects of the CdS layer which eclipse other limiting factors in this technology. Following the description of the predictors that are involved in the V_{oc} model selected as optimal, and by analyzing the correlations between these predictors, it can be concluded that they account for the same physical effect, associated with surface defect states in the CdS layer. To deepen into this matter, a more careful data treatment of the RS defect band over the main CdS-LO (Figure 9a) under 442 nm was performed by calculating the relative intensity of this band in the normalized Raman spectra (i.e. the intensity of all the Raman peaks is normalized to the intensity of the main LO peak at 300 cm^{-1}). This allowed excluding the influence of the CdS layer thickness from the calculations and reducing the dimensionality of the process to a single predictor linear trend (Figure 9b). As anticipated, a clear connection is observed between the intensity of defect band from the PL spectra of CdS layer and the V_{oc} of the solar cell devices. As already mentioned, the subtle alterations in the defect properties of the CdS layer could potentially arise from minor temperature fluctuations during the chemical bath deposition (CBD) process, possibly attributed to the process geometry.^[67,68]

The linear tendency observed in Figure 9b, without any clear saturation, opens the question on how much the V_{oc} of the kesterite PV devices could be improved if this defect band is reduced. This can be estimated by fitting the mean spectra of the measured data in Figure 4 using a combination of individual Lorentzian peaks for each of the individual contributions (Figure 9a). In this way, it is possible to separate the contribution of the CdS Def1 band from the CdS LO peak, allowing the calculation of the minimum expected contribution in that specific region. This region corresponds to the left tail of the CdS LO peak, and the calculated area from this region, i.e., the minimum expected area (for this

characterization technique), results in a predicted V_{oc} value of 521 ± 26 mV, where the standard deviation is extracted from the standard deviation of the measured V_{oc} data. Thus, it is possible to generate a normal distribution centered in the predicted V_{oc} value (see Figure S7) and, from this distribution, infer the expected PCE of the devices assuming that the J_{sc} and FF are kept constant (see Figure 9c). It is concluded that the efficiency of the devices could be improved by 2% (absolute) over the mean value. Even though this is just an exercise and even more it does not allow to estimate the possible improvement in the homogeneity of the process, it emphasizes the importance and shows how significant the small fluctuations in the CdS layers affect the final performance of the devices.

Figure 9: Correlation between the descriptive parameters obtained for the solar cells in this study: a) Mean spectrum of the 392 Raman measurements under 442 nm, including the individual Lorentzian fitted peaks. The area surrounded with the green dashed line represents the contribution of the defect band, and the blue solid area represents the remaining area once the defect is subtracted. b) Correlation between the relative integrated intensity of CdS Def1 band and the V_{oc} of the devices. The red dot shows the expected V_{oc} if the CdS defect is suppressed. c) Inferred optoelectronic parameters of the solar cells if the CdS defect band is reduced to its minimum.

3 Conclusion

In conclusion, this work has shown how a supervised machine learning aided algorithm based on the analysis of real experimental data obtained through spectroscopic techniques can enhance the knowledge in complicated systems, such as the intricate interplay of the optoelectronic properties and defect characteristics in the CZTSe/CdS interface. The investigation of large-area samples has unraveled an unexpected lack of direct correlation between the V_{oc} of the devices and the quality of the CZTSe absorber layer, and revealed the defects in the CdS layer as the main factor governing the V_{oc} . In fact, the defects located at the CdS surface exhibit a clear correlation with V_{oc} , indicating their pivotal role in device performance and the need of controlling them to minimize the cell-to-module efficiency gap when scaling-up the technology. The non-saturated linear correlation between the CdS defects and the V_{oc} allowed estimating that the efficiency of the kesterite thin film PV devices could be improved by 2% (absolute) if such defects were avoided. This shows one of the possible ways that need to be followed for the further improvement of the record efficiencies in the kesterite PV technology, especially with its future scale-up and industrialization in mind. The comprehensive analysis shown

in this work emphasizes the importance of adopting a holistic approach in the development of efficient thin film solar cells, laying the groundwork for enhanced device design, optimization and opening the door to automatic research and in-line automated quality control in future production lines.

4 Methodology

4.1 Material preparation

Device fabrication started by depositing a metallic Mo back contact on top of a 10×10 cm² soda lime glass substrate by DC magnetron sputtering (Alliance Concept CT100). This was followed by the deposition of metallic Cu/Sn/Cu/Zn elemental stack precursors by DC magnetron sputtering (Alliance Concept AC540). The thickness of the different layers of the precursor stack was chosen to achieve a Cu-poor and Zn-rich composition (see Table 1). The 10×10 cm² sample was then cut into 5×5 cm² pieces and then reactively annealed under a Se + Sn atmosphere to form the CZTSe absorber. Chemical etching treatments were used to selectively remove secondary phases and passivate the surface, as reported elsewhere.^[26] The solar cells were completed with a CdS buffer layer deposited by chemical bath deposition with reduced layer growth kinetics due to the use of cadmium nitrate precursor salts, as described elsewhere.^[60] After the buffer layer deposition, window layers of i-ZnO and In₂O₃-SnO₂ (ITO) were deposited by pulsed DC magnetron sputtering (Alliance Concept CT100). The sheet resistance measured by four-probe method is shown in Table 1. Individual 3×3 mm² solar cells were mechanically isolated from each other using a manual microdiamond scribe (OEG MR200), resulting in a total of 196 cells per sample. Following this methodology a top 8.4% PCE was obtained (Figure S8 and S9) with a median PCE = 7.5 % with S.D. = (±0.5) %. The reduction in efficiency compared to the previous record values at small area is associated with the up-scaling of the process.

In this work two different samples (A and B), fabricated with a 2-months difference using the same deposition parameters, were used to evaluate the intrinsic process deviations in two separated deposition runs. Figure 10 shows a picture of the samples used in this work.

Figure 10: Pictures of A (left) and B (right) samples used in this study.

4.2 Materials and device characterization

The composition of the absorber layers was determined using an X-ray fluorescence (XRF) system (Fischerscope XVD) calibrated by inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy (ICP-MS). XRF measurements were performed using a collimator of 3 mm diameter in a 5x5 point grid scanning the entire area of the samples (5x5 cm²), using an accelerating voltage of 50 kV, a Ni10 filter to reduce the background signal, and an integration time per measurement point of 45 s. The minor differences between the samples are shown in Table 1 and relate to the macro data extracted from the absorber material, with the composition and thickness of each sample extrapolated from XRF measurements.

Table 1: Absorber chemical composition and characteristics of the window layer in the two 5x5 cm² samples used in this work. The criterion for quantifying the error is 2 σ .

Sample	A	B
Absorber	CZTSe	
Thickness [nm]	1570 \pm 20	1720 \pm 20
Cu/(Zn+Sn)	0.72 \pm 0.04	0.69 \pm 0.04
Zn/Sn	1.09 \pm 0.04	1.03 \pm 0.04
Se/Me	1.28 \pm 0.04	1.22 \pm 0.04
Front Contact	i-ZnO/ITO	
Thickness [nm]	312 \pm 10	312 \pm 10
Sheet Resistance [Ω/\square]	62.5	46.5

The acquisition of the Raman spectroscopy (RS) signal was done with an optimized UV-Vis spectroscopic systems based on a custom Raman-PL probe-head designed at IREC attached to a Horiba Jobin Yvon FHR640 monochromator coupled with an open electrode CCD detector. A $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 442$ nm (from He-Cd gas laser) and a $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 532$ nm (frequency stabilized YAG:Nd solid state laser) were employed to acquire the signals from the CdS and CZTSe, respectively. The use of an unpolarized laser beam minimized the influence of the crystalline orientation on the spectra. The position of the Raman peaks was corrected by imposing the main peak of monocrystalline Si to 520 cm⁻¹, the FWHM of this peak is 5.2-5.5 cm⁻¹ (Figure S10). The measurements of Photoluminescence spectroscopy (PL) in the NIR range for the CZTSe absorber layer were performed using the same custom probe head attached to a SOL 1.7 spectrometer from B&W Tek and under $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 532$ nm (frequency stabilized YAG:Nd solid state laser) excitation. The CdS emission bands were measured by a Horiba Jobin Yvon IHR320 monochromator coupled with an CCD detector and under $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 442$ nm (from He-Cd gas laser). The PL spectra intensity was calibrated using a NIST calibrated stabilized Tungsten-Halogen Lamp (Figure S11), and the position of the X-axis is calibrated using neon spectral lamp. The custom probe-head employed enabled the quasi-simultaneous acquisition of RS and PL spectroscopy measurements at the same point (i.e., spatially correlated), the probe-head is attached to an X-Y-Z motorized table with micrometric precision movements. The table is programable to any desired pattern, and in the case of this study the pattern employed is from left to right and bottom to top in the sample surface, as schematically shown in Figure S12. For both cases, a systematic laser power density study was performed to avoid thermal effects in the spectra. A power of around

4 mW with a ≈ 70 μm laser spot diameter was used. All the spectroscopic characterizations were performed on the complete devices, to ensure that the structural data corresponds to the final materials that give the final optoelectronic performance.

Micrographs were acquired in top and cross-sectional view configuration employing a Zeiss Series Auriga field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM equipment), employing an acceleration voltage of 5 kV and working distances of 3-5 mm.

Current density-voltage (J-V) measurements were performed on the complete devices using a Sun 3000 AAA solar simulator from Abet Technology (uniform illumination area of 15×15 cm^2) calibrated with a Si reference solar cell (RERA Solutions) under AM1.5 illumination and at 25 °C. The Reference cell is measured at the start of the measurement protocol several times to ensure the stabilization of the solar simulator lamp and ensure the irradiation conditions (Figure S13). All the measurements are performed in forward scanning direction.

The use of these standards guarantee that the variations observed in the measurements of the samples and relevant for this study are due to changes in material properties and not due to measurement uncertainty.

5 Acknowledgements

Co-funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement No. 101058459 Platform-ZERO). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The project on which these results are based has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 952982 (Custom-Art project). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 801342 (Tecniospring INDUSTRY) and the Government of Catalonia's Agency for Business Competitiveness (ACCIÓ). This work is part of the project SCALING (PID2022-138434OB-C52) funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ FEDER, UE. This project has received funding from the MCIN/AEI/FEDER (SCALING PID2022-138434OB-C52). Authors from IREC belong to the MNT-Solar Consolidated Research Group of the "Generalitat de Catalunya" (ref. 2021 SGR 01286) and are grateful to European Regional Development Funds (ERDF, FEDER Programa Competitivitat de Catalunya 2007-2013). M.G. acknowledges the financial support from MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and from FSE+ within the Ramón y Cajal (RYC2022-035588-I) program.

6 References

- [1] I. Mathews, S. N. Kantareddy, T. Buonassisi, I. M. Peters, *Joule* **2019**, 3, 1415.
- [2] A. Ghosh, *J. Clean. Prod.* **2020**, 276, 123343.
- [3] H. Dinesh, J. M. Pearce, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2016**, 54, 299.
- [4] J. A. Kinnaird, P. A. M. Nex, In *Routledge Handbook of the Extractive Industries and Sustainable Development*, Routledge, London, UK, pp. 13-33, **2022**.
- [5] T. D. Lee, A. U. Ebong, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2017**, 70, 1286.

- [6] M. A. Green, E. D. Dunlop, J. Hohl-Ebinger, M. Yoshita, N. Kopidakis, X. Hao, *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.* **2022**, *30*, 3.
- [7] C. Candelise, M. Winkler, R. Gross, *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.* **2012**, *20*, 816.
- [8] A. Wang, N. L. Chang, K. Sun, C. Xue, R. J. Egan, J. Li, C. Yan, J. Huang, H. Rong, C. Ramsden, X. Hao, *Sustain. Energy Fuels* **2021**, *5*, 1044.
- [9] J. Li, K. Sun, X. Yuan, J. Huang, M. A. Green, X. Hao, *npj Flex. Electron.* **2023**, *7*, 16.
- [10] S. Tripathi, S. Maurya, B. Kumar, D. K. Dwivedi, In *2020 International Conference on Electrical and Electronics Engineering (ICE3)*, IEEE, pp. 588–591, **2020**.
- [11] J. Andrade-Arvizu, V. Izquierdo-Roca, I. Becerril-Romero, P. Vidal-Fuentes, R. Fonoll-Rubio, Y. Sánchez, M. Placidi, L. Calvo-Barrio, O. Vigil-Galán, E. Saucedo, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, *11*, 32945.
- [12] J. Andrade-Arvizu, R. Fonoll-Rubio, Y. Sánchez, I. Becerril-Romero, C. Malerba, M. Valentini, L. Calvo-Barrio, V. Izquierdo-Roca, M. Placidi, O. Vigil-Galán, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, E. Saucedo, Z. Jehl Li-Kao, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *3*, 10362.
- [13] J. Andrade-Arvizu, R. Fonoll-Rubio, V. Izquierdo-Roca, I. Becerril-Romero, D. Sylla, P. Vidal-Fuentes, Z. J. Li-Kao, A. Thomere, S. Giraldo, K. Tiwari, S. Resalati, M. Guc, M. Placidi, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2022**, *14*, 1177.
- [14] Jiazheng Zhou, Xiao Xu, Huijue Wu, Jinlin Wang, Licheng Lou, Kang Yin, Yuancai Gong, Jiangjian Shi, Yanhong Luo, Dongmei Li, Hao Xin, Qingbo Meng, *Nat. Energy* **2023**, *8*, 526.
- [15] Jiangjian Shi, Jinlin Wang, Fanqi Meng, Jiazheng Zhou, Xiao Xu, Kang Yin, Licheng Lou, Menghan Jiao, Bowen Zhang, Huijue Wu, Yanhong Luo, Dongmei Li, Qingbo Meng, *arXiv* **2023**.
- [16] Jinlin Wang, Licheng Lou, Kang Yin, Fanqi Meng, Xiao Xu, Menghan Jiao, Bowen Zhang, Jiangjian Shi, Huijue Wu, Yanhong Luo, Dongmei Li, Qingbo Meng. *arXiv:2404.05974v1 [cond-mat.mtrl-sci]* **2024**
- [17] Y. Qi, N. Wei, Y. Li, D. Kou, W. Zhou, Z. Zhou, Y. Meng, S. Yuan, L. Han, S. Wu., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2024**, *34*, 2308333.
- [18] S. Schorr, G. Gurieva, M. Guc, M. Dimitrievska, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, V. Izquierdo-Roca, C. S. Schnohr, J. Kim, W. Jo, J. M. Merino, *J. Phys. Energy* **2020**, *2*, 012002.
- [19] J. Li, J. Huang, F. Ma, H. Sun, J. Cong, K. Privat, R. F. Webster, S. Cheong, Y. Yao, R. L. Chin, X. Yuan, M. He, K. Sun, H. Li, Y. Mai, Z. Hameiri, N. J. Ekins-Daukes, R. D. Tilley, T. Unold, M. A. Green, X. Hao, *Nat. Energy* **2022**, *7*, 754.
- [20] S. Giraldo, Z. Jehl, M. Placidi, V. Izquierdo-Roca, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, E. Saucedo, *Adv. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, 1806692.
- [21] K. Nisika Kaur, M. Kumar, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2020**, *8*, 21547.
- [22] Y. Gong, Q. Zhu, B. Li, S. Wang, B. Duan, L. Lou, C. Xiang, E. Jedlicka, R. Giridharagopal, Y. Zhou, Q. Dai, W. Yan, S. Chen, Q. Meng, H. Xin, *Nat. Energy* **2022**, *7*, 966.
- [23] V. Bermudez, A. Perez-Rodriguez, *Nat. Energy* **2018**, *3*, 466.
- [24] P.L.J. Gunter, J.W. Niemantsverdriet, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A* **1995**, *13*, 1290.
- [25] R. Fonoll-Rubio, J. Andrade-Arvizu, J. Blanco-Portals, I. Becerril-Romero, M. Guc, E. Saucedo, F. Peiró, L. Calvo-Barrio, M. Ritzer, C. S. Schnohr, M. Placidi, S. Estradé, V. Izquierdo-Roca, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2021**, *14*, 507.
- [26] Bhatti, S.; Manzoor, H. U.; Michel, B.; Bonilla, R. S.; Abrams, R.; Zoha, A.; Hussain, S.; Ghannam, R. *Adv. Energy Sustain. Res.* **2023**, *4* (10).
- [27] Suthar, R.; T, A.; Karak, S. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2023**, *11* (41), 22248–22258.
- [28] Zbinden, O.; Knapp, E.; Tress, W. *Sol. RRL* **2024**, *8* (6), 1–8.
- [29] (1) Sutar, S. S.; Patil, S. M.; Kadam, S. J.; Kamat, R. K.; Kim, D.; Dongale, T. D. *ACS Omega* **2021**, *6* (44), 29982–29992.
- [30] Karade, V. C.; Sutar, S. S.; Shin, S. W.; Suryawanshi, M. P.; Jang, J. S.; Gour, K. S.; Kamat, R. K.; Yun, J. H.; Dongale, T. D.; Kim, J. H. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2023**,

- 33 (41), 1–11.
- [31] Grau-Luque, E.; Becerril-Romero, I.; Atlan, F.; Huber, D.; Harnisch, M.; Zimmermann, A.; Pérez-Rodríguez, A.; Guc, M.; Izquierdo-Roca, V. *Small Methods* **2024**, 2301573, 1–17.
- [32] Grau-Luque, E.; Anefnaf, I.; Benhaddou, N.; Fonoll-Rubio, R.; Becerril-Romero, I.; Aazou, S.; Saucedo, E.; Sekkat, Z.; Perez-Rodriguez, A.; Izquierdo-Roca, V.; Guc, M. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2021**, 9 (16).
- [33] Im, J.; Lee, S.; Ko, T. W.; Kim, H. W.; Hyon, Y. K.; Chang, H. *npj Comput. Mater.* **2019**, 5 (1), 1–8..
- [34] Liu, Z.; Rolston, N.; Flick, A. C.; Colburn, T. W.; Ren, Z.; Dauskardt, R. H.; Buonassisi, T. *Joule* **2022**, 6 (4), 834–849.
- [35] Wu, Y.; Guo, J.; Sun, R.; Min, J. *npj Comput. Mater.* **2020**, 6 (1), 120.
- [36] Gong, Y.; Zhu, Q.; Li, B.; Wang, S.; Duan, B.; Lou, L.; Xiang, C.; Jedlicka, E.; Giridharagopal, R.; Zhou, Y.; Dai, Q.; Yan, W.; Chen, S.; Meng, Q.; Xin, H. *Nat. Energy* **2022**, 7 (10), 966–977.
- [37] R. Fonoll-Rubio, I. Becerril-Romero, P. Vidal-Fuentes, E. Grau-Luque, F. Atlan, A. Perez-Rodriguez, V. Izquierdo-Roca, M. Guc, *Sol. RRL* **2022**, 6, 2200235.
- [38] Enric Grau-Luque, Ikram Anefnaf, Nada Benhaddou, Robert Fonoll-Rubio, Ignacio Becerril-Romero, Safae Aazou, Edgardo Saucedo, Zouheir Sekkat, Alejandro Perez-Rodriguez, Victor Izquierdo-Roca, Maxim Guc, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2021**, 9, 10466.
- [39] Robert Fonoll-Rubio, Stefan Paetel, Enric Grau-Luque, Ignacio Becerril-Romero, Rafael Mayer, Alejandro Pérez-Rodríguez, Maxim Guc, Victor Izquierdo-Roca, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2022**, 12, 2103163.
- [40] M. Dimitrievska, A. Fairbrother, X. Fontané, T. Jawhari, V. Izquierdo-Roca, E. Saucedo, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2014**, 104, 021901.
- [41] S. López-Marino, Y. Sánchez, M. Placidi, A. Fairbrother, M. Espindola-Rodríguez, X. Fontané, V. Izquierdo-Roca, J. López-García, L. Calvo-Barrio, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, E. Saucedo, *Chem. - A Eur. J.* **2013**, 19, 14814.
- [42] O. Prakash, S. Umapathy, *J. Chem. Phys.* **2023**, 158, 134719.
- [43] K. Gong, D. F. Kelley, A. M. Kelley, *J. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, 147, 224702.
- [44] F. Atlan, I. Becerril-Romero, S. Giraldo, V. Rotaru, Y. Sánchez, G. Gurieva, S. Schorr, E. Arushanov, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, V. Izquierdo-Roca, M. Guc, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* **2023**, 249, 112046.
- [45] Jan Sendler, Maxime Thevenin, Florian Werner, Alex Redinger, Shuyi Li, Carl Hägglund, Charlotte Platzer-Björkman, Susanne Siebentritt, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2016**, 120, 125701.
- [46] Pedro M. P. Salomé, Paulo A. Fernandes, Joaquim P. Leitão, Marta G. Sousa, Jennifer P. Teixeira, António F. da Cunha, *J. Mater. Sci.* **2014**, 49, 7425.
- [47] J. Márquez-Prieto, M.V. Yakushev, I. Forbes, J. Krustok, P.R. Edwards, V. D. Zhivulko, O. M. Borodavchenko, A. V. Mudryi, M. Dimitrievska, V. Izquierdo-Roca, N. M. Pearsall, R. W. Martin, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cell* **2016**, 152, 42.
- [48] J. F. Scott, T. C. Damen, *Opt. Commun.* **1972**, 5, 410.
- [49] O. Zelaya-Angel, F. d. L. Castillo-Alvarado, J. Avendaño-López, A. Escamilla-Esquivel, G. Contreras-Puente, R. Lozada-Morales, G. Torres-Delgado, *Solid State Commun.* **1997**, 104, 161.
- [50] M. F. Saleem, H. Zhang, Y. Deng, D. Wang, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* **2017**, 48, 224.
- [51] Florian Oliva, Steffen Kretzschmar, Diego Colombara, Sara Tombolato, Carmen Maria Ruiz, Alex Redinger, Edgardo Saucedo, Cédric Broussillou, Thomas Goislard de Monsabert, Thomas Unold, Philip J. Dale, Victor Izquierdo-Roca, Alejandro Pérez-Rodríguez, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cell* **2016**, 158, 168.
- [52] S. Zeiske, C. Kaiser, O. J. Sandberg, T. Ericson, P. Meredith, C. Platzer-Björkman, A. Armin, *Adv. Photonics Res.* **2023**, 4, 2300177.
- [53] J. Trajic, M. Gilic, N. Romcevic, M. Romcevic, G. Stanisic, B. Hadzic, M. Petrovic, Y. S. Yahia, *Sci. Sinter.* **2015**, 47, 145.

- [54] D. Routkevitch, T. L. Haslett, L. Ryan, T. Bigioni, C. Douketis, M. Moskovits, *Chem. Phys.* **1996**, *210*, 343.
- [55] J. J. Shiang, S. H. Risbud, A. P. Alivisatos, *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *98*, 8432.
- [56] M. Kostoglou, N. Andritsos, A. Karabelas, *Thin Solid Films* **2001**, *387*, 115.
- [57] N. Kumar, F. Alam, V. Dutta, *RSC Adv.* **2016**, *6*, 28316.
- [58] G. Kalyuzhny, R. W. Murray, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, *109*, 7012.
- [59] S. R. Cordero, P. J. Carson, R. A. Estabrook, G. F. Strouse, S. K. Buratto, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2000**, *104*, 12137.
- [60] F. Zezza, R. Comparelli, M. Striccoli, M. L. Curri, R. Tommasi, A. Agostiano, M. Della Monica, *Synth. Met.* **2003**, *139*, 597.
- [61] P. Vidal-Fuentes, M. Guc, X. Alcobe, T. Jawhari, M. Placidi, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, E. Saucedo, V. Izquierdo-Roca, *2D Mater.* **2019**, *6*, 045054.
- [62] M. Guc, A. P. Litvinchuk, S. Levchenko, V. Izquierdo-Roca, X. Fontané, M. Y. Valakh, E. Arushanov, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, *Phys. Rev. B* **2014**, *89*, 205205.
- [63] M. Guc, S. Levchenko, V. Izquierdo-Roca, X. Fontané, E. Arushanov, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2013**, *114*, 193514.
- [64] M. Dimitrievska, A. Fairbrother, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, E. Saucedo, V. Izquierdo-Roca, *Acta Mater.* **2014**, *70*, 272.
- [65] Fabian Pedregosa, Gaël Varoquaux, Alexandre Gramfort, Vincent Michel, Bertrand Thirion, Olivier Grisel, Mathieu Blondel, Peter Prettenhofer, Ron Weiss, Vincent Dubourg, Jake Vanderplas, Alexandre Passos, David Cournapeau, Matthieu Brucher, Matthieu Perrot, Édouard Duchesnay, *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* **2011**, *12*, 2825.
- [66] K. Hyon Chol, C. Hyon Ho, K. Yong Jo, S. Gwang Il, *Opt. Mater.* **2021**, *112*, 110790.
- [67] C. Wang, B. Yao, Y. Li, Z. Ding, D. Ma, T. Wang, J. Y. Zhang, D. Zhang, Y. Liu, R. Liu, *Sol. Energy* **2023**, *262*, 111847.
- [68] R. C. Ruiz-Ortega, L. A. Esquivel-Mendez, M. A. Gonzalez-Trujillo, C. Hernandez-Vasquez, Y. Matsumoto, M. D. L. Albor-Aguilera, *ACS Omega* **2023**, *8*, 31725.